

ELEMENTS OF TECHNICAL, SOCIAL, ECONOMIC, CULTURAL IMPACT ON THE ACQUISITION OF OPTIONAL MOUNTAIN PRODUCT QUALITY. OPPORTUNITIES FOR PRODUCERS

Ioan SURDU, Vasile AVĂDĂNEI,

Emanuela Adina COCIȘ, Carmen CĂTUNĂ-BOCA

Mountain Economy Center Vatra Dornei, str. Petreni, no. 49 /
National Institute for Economic Research "Costin C. Kirițescu"
*surdu.ioan@gmail.com; vasileavadanei2004@yahoo.com;;
adinaemanuelacocis@gmail.com; catunacarmen@yahoo.com*

Abstract

The optional indication of origin, Mountain product, has the effect of re-establishing the attitude of producers and consumers towards a series of food products prepared in the mountain area and which thus draw attention to the special qualities of consumption. On the producers' side, it is necessary to adapt and optimize the way they work, store and consume in order for the result of their work to encourage them to become part of a complex process of improving marketing mechanisms in the face of the acute problem of global food, but also the requirements of refinement in the equally complex equation of tourism development. The paper uses the method of questionnaires to assess the expectations of producers after they have registered in the National Register of Mountain Product (RNPM).

The paper aimed to measure the impact of adopting the optional quality name "mountain product" as a way of valuing the life and work of mountain people. A number of 114 people, producers, who work in 19 mountain counties were interviewed. The set of questions included two categories of data: identification data for systematization and statistical interpretations and questions for the structured description of the mountain product. Positive options have emerged in which the opportunity of the mountain product has facilitated the mobilization of mountain families to increase food production according to a plan that eliminates unnecessary or misused operations and resources. Negative options related to the lack of flexibility of producers to meet consumer requirements also resulted.

Keywords: *Mountain product, mountain manufacturer, technology, mountain product classification, mountain product attributes.*

INTRODUCTION

The mountain product is a generic name that can be used by producers of agri-food products in the mountain area in order to mark and highlight their difference from similar products made in the hilly and lowland areas. This differentiation is motivated by the fact that for similar products the realization costs in the mountain area are significantly higher per unit of product.

The mountain realities highlighted elements of both positive and negative particularity on the basic need of the population, that of food. Here are classic and modern food resources, brought and acclimatized, with the skill of housewives to prepare elaborate forms of food for immediate consumption (public food) or with storage for a period of time (food production). The mountain product has been delimited and defined in a wider European context in order to mark an essential feature of the most efficient management of natural resources in the mountain area, through transhumance. The mountain product takes over some of

these elements of cultural heritage and transmits them from generation to generation on food.

For mountain dwellers “*Mountain product*” has created high expectations. On the one hand, a form of product labeling has emerged to facilitate market access. On the other hand, there is no monitoring and control structure and no precedent for deviation from the attestation conditions. However, there are suspicions that some manufacturers do not use genuine mountain resources for the range of products made and supplied.

In a research project funded by the Ministry of Agriculture through the ADER program, a detailed analysis of all aspects and requirements involving safe production, marketing and consumption of safe.

For the space of action of the producers, the problems they will face are developed on several essential aspects. These requirements are not new. They allowed technological deviations that ranked housewives in the preparation of food for family members. When different dishes expand their consumption area outside a household, value packs are activated, and they require, in addition to an increase in the rigor of the preparation method, a greater care in increasing the quality of raw materials in the chain. The expression “from fork to fork” has appeared and enters the rural mountain mentality, in which the food chain is defined as a supply chain starting with the meadow, continuing with care for animals, making food preparations, providing taste and flavor bouquet, creating the experience and memory of the gastronomic event, as well as the digestive transit that must lead to well-being.

STATE OF THE ART

The mountain product has become a food movement on a European scale. The aspects of organization, functioning, consumption, control were regulated (EC 2016, Euromontana 2017). Romania has aligned itself with this practice and has customized the regulations in accordance with national legislative regulations and local or regional cultural aspects (GD 506/2016, ord. 174/2021).

Traceability studies have been carried out to determine the origin of foodstuffs (which are the subject of the mountain product) (Doğu & Şireli, 2016).

The extent to which mountain ecosystems are important for the consumption value of mountain products is studied (Regamey et al., 2012).

Consumer studies have already been conducted on consumer preferences and the willingness to pay a higher price (Mazzocchi & Sali, 2021). In (Finco et al., 2017) the perception of producers and distributors about the mountain product on palpable criteria is presented, as we take it in Fig. 1. There is a diversity of attitudes towards the essential attributes of the mountain product.

In Switzerland, the study of the mountain product aims to segment the categories of producers and consumers, in order to understand consumption priorities (Delley et al., 2020). This is the complementary process of value chain integration which aims to reduce poverty in the rural mountain area (Hoermann et al., 2010).

The cultural value of mountain food products is linked to their history, to the transfer between generations, to the measure of permanence insinuated in everyday life. It is amplified by the specifics of work in post-modern society in which contact with food becomes an expected event on weekends or holidays. This requires producers to assume transparency in production and product traceability.

Fig. 1. Attributes of the mountain product perceived by producers

(Finco, et al., 2016)

THE PRINCIPLE OF THE METHOD

The aspects which are of concern to the manufacturer as regards the physico-chemical and biochemical processes involved in the preparation of preparations with the attribute "mountain product" are distributed as follows:

- intentionality social participation in coagulation process from family to community to obtain product mountain;
- the scope of the activity approach and the interaction with the legal forms of organization and functioning;
- defining a classification that structures mountain products into groups with common characteristics;
- the manufacturer's behavior when going through the preliminary and subsequent stages;
- the need for additional workforce and the necessary skills: from involving family members to hiring specialists;
- technological and control aspect: traceability and reproducibility;
- the attributes of traditionalism and modernity: where cultural compromises are made;
- emotional impact and food role of consumption (taste – taste buds, smell – aromas, appearance – plateau, sound – crunchy, tactile – velvety), satiety/hunger & thirst.

It is obvious that in order to acquire the quality of mountain product supplier, a change of mentality and behavior is necessary. The values of the manufacturer must be re-established in such a way as to clearly show concern for the customer without creating significant deviations in the treatment of the intrinsic attributes of the mountain product.

In this context, the manufacturer's approach and evaluation focused, in an appropriate questionnaire, on 9 issues, grouped as follows (Table 1).

Table 1. Matrix structuring of mountain product attributes

	<i>Effectiveness</i>	<i>Viability</i>	<i>Ability to Integrate</i>
<i>Availability</i>	Interest (<i>a</i>)	Technological attributes (<i>e</i>)	Labor force (<i>c</i>)
<i>Specialization</i>	Typology (<i>b</i>)	Know how (<i>f</i>)	Competences (<i>d</i>)
<i>Identity</i>	Market magnitude (<i>i</i>)	Cultural attributes (<i>h</i>)	Food categories (<i>g</i>)

The following observations are made in the structuring of the subject:

- Horizontally:
 - The *Effectiveness* of the mountain product is given by the types of products classified, the types of products dealt with by the participants in the debate, and the size of the market given by the commercial interest;
 - The *Viability* of the mountain product is given by the available technological attributes, recipes (know how) and the cultural attributes that propel it;
 - The *Ability to integrate* of the mountain product is given by the available labor force (including the labor market), the skills of those engaged in the activity (for compatibility with the market) and the categories of food that are supplied by the market.
- Vertically:
 - The *Availability* of the mountain product is given by the interest of the producers to make it integrate, by the technological attributes, which determine the conformity, and by the people who deal with this activity;
 - The *Specialization* for the realization of the mountain product is given by the classification category (according to RNPM), know-how available by way of inheritance and by the native and acquired competencies of the operator;
 - The *Identity* of the mountain product is given by the notoriety acquired by the size of the market, the strength of the cultural attributes, and by the food diversity as destination.

The typological categories of mountain products were taken from the National Register of Mountain Product (NRMP). These are (in extended and abbreviated terms):

- i. Milk and milk products (milk, in abbreviated form);
- ii. Meat and meat products (meat);
- iii. Vegetables, fruits grown (vegetable);
- iv. Fruits of spontaneous flora and preparations thereof (forest fruits);
- v. Fish and fish products (fish);
- vi. Bee products (beekeeping);
- vii. Bread, bakery, pastries (bakery);
- viii. Herbs for food and health from spontaneous flora (Health herbs);
- ix. Mushrooms from spontaneous flora and preparations from therefrom (mushrooms);
- x. Others, mention which

For each question we proceeded as follows: the question was formulated, a number of answers were formulated, the respondent was invited to give a grade from 1 to 5 to each

variant according to their own criteria (knowledge, experience, requirements). The results were statistically processed and the significance of the results was interpreted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A sample of 128 mountain producers took part in the debate. They were selected from mountain producers who have at least one product that has obtained approval for "Mountain product – optional designation of origin" and are registered in the RNPM. The statistical distribution is presented in Table 2. The distribution by counties was highlighted on the following criteria: number of respondents, gender (male, female), age categories (under 30, between 31–40, 41–50, 51–60, over 60 years), level of education (general, high school, professional, higher).

P1.1. Identification of respondents

Table 2. Statistical attributes of the sample of respondents

County	Respondents	Gender		Age (years)					Education*			
		M	F	Under 30	30–40	40–50	50–60	Over 60	G	L	P	S
AB	5	3	2	0	0	2	3	0	1	2	0	2
AG	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	1
AR	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
BC	7	5	2	1	2	1	1	2	0	4	1	2
BH	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
BN	21	17	4	0	2	2	16	1	15	2	2	2
BV	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	1	0
BZ	6	6	0	0	2	1	1	2	0	3	0	3
CV	12	10	2	1	2	5	1	3	4	1	2	5
DB	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
GJ	4	1	3	0	1	2	1	0	0	2	1	1
HR	3	1	2	0	0	1	2	0	0	1	1	1
MM	31	18	13	0	2	6	19	4	15	7	3	6
MS	3	2	1	0	0	0	2	1	0	2	1	0
NT	10	8	2	1	3	3	2	1	3	3	0	4
PH	5	4	1	0	2	1	2	0	1	0	3	1
SB	3	2	1	0	0	1	2	0	0	1	2	0
SV	5	4	1	0	0	4	1	0	0	0	2	3
VN	3	2	1	0	0	1	0	2	0	1	1	1
VL	3	3	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	2	0	0
Total	128	91	37	3	17	32	55	21	40	35	20	33
%		71.1	28.9	2.3	13.3	25.0	43.0	16.4	31.3	27.3	15.6	25.8

* Education: G= secondary, L = high school, P = professional; S = higher education;

Three questions were asked for statistical data. We mention that the regulations regarding the processing of personal data have been observed.

Examination of the table shows the following observations:

- a. The activity is interesting for 71.1% of men, which reflects the gap in entrepreneurship, but also the gap in receptivity.
- b. According to the age criterion, there is a significant gap in the age under 30 (2.3%); for now, it is a lack of interest for young people. The largest share is represented by the population aged 50–60 years (43%), which has accumulated knowledge about the mountain product, which is filled with nostalgia for traditions and culture and the effort to prevent the installation of disinterest and indifference. There is also the presence of elderly people over 60 years (16.4%) looking for natural, authentic, healthy products.
- c. According to the criterion of studies, there are two polarizations: on the one hand, there is interest from the population without studies, which knows the trade through the genealogical chain; on the other hand, the low share of people with vocational education reflects the lack of support infrastructure for this type of training.

The set of questions led to results and assessments about the realities of the mountain product in the area of the Romanian Carpathians.

a. Areas and level of interest by mountain product classes

Table 3 shows the percentage distribution of the interviewees to become mountain producers and which categories of activity are of interest.

Table 3. Interest in mountain product classes accepted in the RNPM

Scale of interest				
Very low	Low	Middle	High	Excellent
1	2	3	4	5
a. "Milk" class				
57.8%	0.8%	0.0%	0.8%	40.6%
b. "Meat" class				
92.2%	1.6%	0.8%	1.6%	39%
c. Class "Vegetables"				
57.8%	0.0%	0.8%	0.8%	40.6%
d. Class "Forest fruits"				
89.8%	0.8%	0.0%	3.1%	6.3%
e. Class "Fish"				
95.3%	0.0%	0.0%	1.6%	3.1%
f. Class "Apiarian"				
75.8%	0.8%	1.6%	0.8%	21.1%
g. Class "Panification"				
94.5%	0.0%	1.6%	0.0%	3.9%
h. Class "Health herbs"				
90.6%	0.8%	0.0%	1.6%	7.0%

i. Class “Mushrooms”				
93.0%	1.6%	0.0%	0.8%	4.7%
j. Class “Other” (brandy – palinca)				
96.1%	0.8%	0.0%	1.6%	1.6%

The results show in the last column the sensitivity of producers for certain types of resources. The fields are noticeable: milk, vegetables–fruits, beekeeping. The other columns show an attitude of gradual indifference on the same picture of domains. The fields of Bakery, Mushrooms, Herbs, Fish stand out. Some do not have raw materials in the area (bakery), others require expensive arrangements (fish), others require special permits (fish), others are in the forest area and collection is illegal (mushrooms, herbs).

It should be noted that in the field of fish farming is not practiced at all the artificial population with brood in running water, as a measure to stimulate production.

b. Areas of activity (classes) on which the mountain product was dedicated

Under these conditions, the distribution of domain respondents is presented as in Table 4, which highlights strong traditional activities. At the same time, food control requirements have increased, which has restricted activity in some areas. An example is meat and meat products. They do not appear in the register, but are practiced on the mountain market. A solution for slaughtering animals using mobile slaughterhouses is being regulated.

Table 4. Distribution of respondents by mountain product classes defined in the RNPM;

Milk	Meat	Vegetables	Forest fruits	Fish	Apiarian	Panification	Health herbs	Mushrooms	Other
35.1%	1.4%	37.2%	2.7%	0.7%	15.5%	0.7%	1.4%	2.7%	2.7%

c. The social component of the mountain product

In general, the mountain product is a family activity. The need for labor seems to be enough, so all the benefits remain in the household. Some activities are larger in scope and employ staff outside the family: permanent employees (in large-scale businesses with a continuous need for labor) or seasonal employees (where the viability of resources is limited: agricultural work, harvesting, processing fast).

Table 5 presents the employment situation of producers who have agreed to participate in the debate.

Table 5. Personnel resources for the realization of the mountain product (people)

Family members	Permanent employees	Seasonal employees	Independent consultants/ experts	Authorized individuals	Other categories	Total
315	155	197	0	0	0	667
47.2%	23.2%	29.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	

The data in the table show that the activity of making the mountain product is strictly family. It does not involve consultants, experts, service providers. With rare exceptions, seasonal employees are used. What the table does not show is the traditional *claca* (group work) in which volunteering is applied in archaic forms

d. The need for skills of the mountain product

Reference is made to the qualities of the human factor (professional qualities and skill) regarding technological and know-how involvement; Table 6 shows the diverse reaction of the participants in the debate.

Table 6. The technical, creative, skillful qualities of the producers

Scale of interest				
Very low	Very low	Very low	Very low	Very low
1	2	3	4	5
a. Criterion "High specialization/qualification on the product"				
17.2%	13.3%	28.1%	14.8%	26.6%
b. Criterion "Adaptation to modern technologies/development of new products"				
14.1%	14.1%	30.5%	21.9%	20.3%
c. Criterion "Innovation, creativity, attraction to novelty, talent"				
19.5%	16.4%	31.4%	18.8%	14.8%
d. Criterion "Stability, consistency, pragmatism"				
16.4%	5.5%	4.7%	14.8%	58.6%
e. Criterion "Good manager/administrator, initiative spirit"				
16.4%	5.5%	17.2%	39.1%	21.9%
f. Criterion "Well-known person, experience/business spirit, negotiator, salesman"				
18.8%	7.0%	16.4%	39.1%	18.8%
g. Criterion "Knowledge of the supply chain, owner of relationships (trade, markets)"				
21.9%	3.9%	20.3%	36.7%	17.2%

Traditional products have been treated and developed in analogy with the knowledge gained in what is called the "school of life". Mountain product practitioners do not go to school and do not value it. The "mountain product club" system also does not involve monitoring and control elements, even though a good practice guide has been developed in the meantime. Only pragmatism is treated with care and seriousness, because it refers to success factors.

e. Technological peculiarities in the realization of the mountain product

It refers to the technological elements as success factors for the mountain products made. Possible advances in technological improvement, which ensures reproducibility, associated with traditional aspects that create diversity in product quality are presented. Table 7 shows the technological approach of mountain producers.

Table 7. Positioning of mountain producers in relation to technological peculiarities

Scale of interest				
Very low	Very low	Very low	Very low	Very low
1	2	3	4	5
a. Criterion "Artisanal, archaic techniques/technologies"				
38.3%	14.8%	10.9%	12.5%	23.4%
b. Criterion "Modernized artisanal techniques/technologies with partial control of the parameters"				
45.3%	7.0%	8.6%	18.0%	21.1%
c. Criterion "New techniques/technologies with rigorous control of the production flow"				
44.5%	10.9%	10.2%	15.6%	18.8%
d. Criterion "Reproducibility"				
15.6%	10.2%	34.4%	24.2%	15.6%
e. Criterion "Flexibility of the production process"				
12.5%	11.7%	35.2%	22.7%	18.0%
f. Criterion "Level of automation"				
48.4,6%	14.1%	15.6%	12.5%	9.4%
g. Criterion "Manual, customized production"				
9.4%	7.8%	5.5%	10.2%	67.2%

The table shows that manufacturers are not enthusiastic about technological features. Whether they are archaic or modernized with a progressive technological level, the attitude towards technology in relation to the mountain product is of little interest. The automation that would transfer operating systems from manual to robotic is not viewed optimistically either. Instead, reproducibility and flexibility are of interest. Of great interest is the personalized manual production, but it seems that the respondents did not understand the question.

f. Peculiarities of the recipes on the basis of which the mountain product is made

Another distinction that gives specificity to the mountain product is the recipe. It depends on the resource base and the particularities of the additions that give it the expected value from the mountain product. Table 8 shows the sources for recipes and their particular elements that give them value.

Table 8. Diversity of recipes for the mountain product

Scale of interest				
Very low	Very low	Very low	Very low	Very low
1	2	3	4	5
a. Criterion "Ancestor / traditional recipes, preserved with holiness"				
11.7%	8.6%	3.1%	4.7%	71.9%

b. Criterion “New research-based recipes”				
50.4%	7.6%	0.0%	26.7%	15.3%
c. Criterion “Recipes required by the market”				
42.2%	0.8%	10.9%	19.5%	26.6%
d. Criterion “Recipes recommended by nutritionists”				
55.5%	8.6%	13.3%	14.8%	7.8%
e. Criterion “Unique recipes”				
57.8%	6.3%	3.9%	6.3%	25.8%
f. Criterion “Strange, fanciful, crazy recipes”				
79.7%	11.7%	6.3%	1.6%	0.8%

There is an important basis of recipes inherited in the family or in the community, which ensures a certain reproducibility in the skill of the manufacturer. But there are also recipes obtained through successive research and experimentation.

There is a hilarious element to the criterion “recipes demanded by the market” which confirms that we know what we put in the recipe, but we do not know what comes out in the end, and what we sell seems to be the product of a coincidence.

g. The food impact of the mountain product

Reference is made to the appreciation of mountain products made, in relation to the aspects of defining food as a destination or as an artisanal/industrial approach.

Table 9. Categories of food that are the subject of the mountain product

Scale of interest				
Very low	Very low	Very low	Very low	Very low
1	2	3	4	5
a. Criterion “Food for the soul, for special events”				
10.9%	16.4%	28.1%	15.6%	28.9%
b. Criterion “Food of necessity”				
5.5%	2.3%	9.4%	14.1%	68.8%
c. Criterion “Food with high nutritional value”				
3.9%	4.7%	2.3%	13.3%	75.8%
d. Criterion “Special food for people with various health conditions”				
7.8%	10.2%	17.2%	21.1%	43.8%
e. Criterion “Healthy food”				
2.3%	0.8%	2.3%	3.9%	90.6%
f. Criterion “Artisanal food”				
35.9%	15.6%	10.2%	7.0%	31.3%
g. Criterion “Commercial/industrial food”				
52.3%	22.7%	12.5%	5.5%	7.0%

Table 9 describes the attitude of producers towards the type of food resulting to compare it with the technological product and commercial demand. The criterion “Food for the soul, for special events” has no spectacular values because it is not perceived as such. More relevant is the criterion “Food of necessity”. This positioning is what disadvantages the mountain product compared to similar assortments on the market. The “Healthy Food” criterion also balances the commercial advantages.

h. The natural and cultural values of the mountain product

In general, the participants in the debate are aware of the natural and cultural attributes of the mountain product and correlate their concerns with the advantages of living in the mountain area. Formal expressions are used: recipes from the elderly, therapeutic value, health merchant, passion and source of income, natural product, valuable product, inherited brand (cheeses, Groşani milk)), preservation of meadows, preservation of traditions, natural and cultural treasure, taste like at home mom, etc.

i. The market

Mountain products have a small market: in the locality, at the market in nearby cities, at fairs, events, festivals, on a list of loyal customers, own store. They often resort to store networks, home delivery by courier.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study aimed to highlight the elements associated with the involvement of the manufacturer in the general equation which includes resources, production, refining, storage, marketing, consumption. The result is 5 vector sizes each with 7 components associated with the mountain product that cover the diversity of resources, methods, products, technical, commercial and cultural elements.

The study highlighted the need for a 4-component work package: training, training, practical applications and marketing for mountain product actors, as combining a well-established but traditional rural activity with the demands of a dynamic market requires specific knowledge.

The mountain product, through its actors must go through the entrepreneurial part because it was found that one of the weaknesses is the way of presentation and negotiation for a good price to make the business attractive. This results from the measurement of food impact (Table 9).

In terms of technology, the mountain product suffers from the restrained attitude of the manufacturer to approach a stricter monitoring of the manufacturing process. It is, in particular, the ambient temperature that brings negative influences on the product and makes one lot not look like another. The reproducibility of the characteristics from one batch to another is important.

The recipes used must highlight both the elements resulting from traditional practices and those of alignment with modern practices, evolved from a nutritional point of view. Manufacturers need to make an effort to keep up with the current food market.

Acknowledgments

This article is being developed as part of the ADER 17.1.2 project. – “Mountain product as a model to support the added value of products made by farmers in the mountain area, in order to sustainably develop mountain farms” funded by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development.

REFERENCES

- ***, Euromontana 2017. Euromontana – mountain products. <http://www.euromontana.org/en/working-themes/mountainproducts/>. Accesat 01.09.2021
- ***, European Commission. (2014). Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 665/2014 of 11 March 2014 supplementing Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to conditions of use of the optional quality term “mountain product.” Official Journal of the European Union, 1–3
- ***, HOTĂRÂREA nr. 506 din 20 iulie 2016 privind stabilirea cadrului instituțional și a unor măsuri pentru punerea în aplicare a Regulamentului delegat (UE) nr. 665/2014 al Comisiei din 11 martie 2014 de completare a Regulamentului (UE) nr. 1.151/2012 al Parlamentului European și al Consiliului în ceea ce privește condițiile de utilizare a mențiunii de calitate facultative “produs montan”; <https://www.madr.ro/docs/ind-alimen-tara/2019/produs-montan/hot-506-din-20-iulie-2016-produs-montan-actualizata.pdf>
- ***, ORDIN Nr. 174 din 20 iulie 2021 privind aprobarea Procedurii de verificare a conformității datelor cuprinse în caietul de sarcini în vederea acordării dreptului de utilizare a mențiunii de calitate facultative “produs montan” și de realizare a controlului în vederea verificării respectării legislației europene și naționale de către operatorii economici care au obținut dreptul de utilizare a respectivei mențiuni; <https://www.madr.ro/docs/ind-alimentara/2019/produs-montan/ORDIN-nr-174-din-20-iulie-2021-.pdf>
- A Finco, D Bentivoglio, G Bucci**, 2016, A label for mountain products? Let's turn it over to producers and retailers, *Quality – Access to Success*, 18, 2017,
- Adrienne Grêt-Regamey, Sibyl Hanna Brunner, Felix Kienast**, 2012, *Mountain Ecosystem Services: Who Cares?*, Mountain Research and Development, 32(S1): (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1659/MRD-JOURNAL-D-10-00115.S1>
- Brigitte Hoermann Dyutiman Choudhary Dhrupad Choudhury Michael Kollmair**, 2010, Integrated Value Chain Development as a Tool for Poverty Alleviation in Rural Mountain Areas, An analytical and strategic framework, in International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development, Kathmandu, June 2010
- Chiara Mazzocchi, Guido Sali**, 2021, Supporting mountain agriculture through “mountain product” label: a choice experiment approach, *Environment Development and Sustainability*, (2021), https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351500387_Supporting_mountain_agriculture_through_mountain_product_label_a_choice_experiment_approach
- Mathilde Delley* and Thomas A. Brunner**, 2020, *A segmentation of Swiss fluid milk consumers and suggestions for target product concepts*, in *Journal of Dairy Science*, v. 103, n 4
- Özbay Doğu, U. Tanse Şireli**, 2016, Determination tools of origin in the food traceability, *Journal of Food and Health Science*, 2(3): 140–146 (2016)
- <https://www.madr.ro/docs/ind-alimentara/2019/produs-montan/Ghid-produs-montan-update-07.06.2019.pdf>, consultat 29.08.2021
- <https://www.madr.ro/industrie-alimentara/sisteme-de-calitate-europene-si-indicatii-geografice/produse-agricole-si-alimentare/produs-montan.html>, consultat 1 mai 2021